

Impact of Training and Development on the Performance of Employees and Organization at Ministry of Agriculture, Irrigation and Livestock of Afghanistan

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Abstract:- Training and Development (T&D) is an important strategic approach for improving efficiency and productivity of employees and organization, and organizations continue to increase their training budgets year after year in the belief that it will give them a competitive advantage. The main objective of this study is to examine the impact of T&D on performance of employees and organization at Ministry of Agriculture, Irrigation and Livestock (MAIL) of Afghanistan. To determine the influence of all independent variables on overall organizational and employee's performance, three hypotheses were tested. Three hypotheses had a significant impact on organizational performance. Furthermore, the ineffectiveness of employee T&D decreases the efficiency of the organization, as organizations rely on providing people with the right skills, attitudes, and capacities in order to achieve their objectives. The participants for this research, which took a quantitative approach, were chosen using a convenient sampling process. As a result, data was gathered by the use of a questionnaire. The target participants were limited to the employees of MAIL. These hypotheses were proved through collecting primary data and with the aid of a literature review. Overall outcome for Hypothesis indicate that, H₁: proved that T&D has statistically significant impact on performance of employees and organization, H₂: proved that T&D has statistically significant impact on the satisfaction of the employees, H₃: proved that design and delivery of training has statistically significant impact on behavior and knowledge of employees.

Keywords:- Training, Development, Afghanistan, Employee's performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Employee training and development is an important topic these days because it benefits the company in a variety of ways. Some staff or employees are assigned to implement regular organization functions and day-to-day maintenance. This can only be accomplished if the workers are given adequate T&D (Abogsesa & Kaushik, 2018). T&D is an important strategic instrument for improving employee efficiency, and businesses continue to raise their training

budgets on a yearly basis in the hopes of gaining a competitive advantage (Falola et al. 2014). The main goal of each organization is to increase its efficiency, but this is impossible to do without effective employee performance. As a result, the performance management system was implemented as a management reform to fix and resolve performance issues that companies have (Tahir et al. ,2014). Globalization, technological advances, political and economic conditions have all intensified competition for businesses. As a result, these companies are giving training to their workers as one of the ways to prepare them to adapt to the above-mentioned rises and thus improve their efficiency (Shigenobu & Ikeda,2009). Human resource development is a systematic approach to enhancing organizational efficiency through T&D of employees, as well as career and organizational development (Khalifa, 2015). T&D is the process of acquiring or transferring the skills, knowledge, and abilities required to perform a particular activity, as a result, T&D benefiting both employers and workers are strategic objectives and therefore much wider (Niazi,2011). T&D encourage workers' effort and innovation, as well as preventing workforce obsolescence, which can be caused by age, personality, or a person's failure to adjust to technological changes (Obisi & Ph,2011). Training is the method of improving and expanding an employee's abilities, expertise, and knowledge. They claimed that training can actually happen after which the need and goals for it have been determined (Obisi & Ph, 2011). In today's competitive world, any organization's ability to train its human resources to be inventive, creative, and innovative, and can certainly improve efficiency and enhance competitive advantage. T&D are critical to an organization's effectiveness.

A. Introduction about the Ministry of Agriculture, Irrigation and Livestock, Afghanistan

MAIL is one of the ministries of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan. MAIL is working on the expansion and modernization of agriculture, livestock and horticulture. Since agriculture is the primary source of income for 80% of the country's population, the Afghan Ministry of Agriculture is a constantly striving to boost agriculture, productivity, and crop farming. To help farmers, control natural resources, and improve agricultural development, the ministry launches programs in agriculture, livestock, and

horticulture. Development and launch of higher-value economic crops, improving conventional goods, recognizing and distributing farm-tailored land technologies, enhancing cooperative projects, agricultural economics, and export with marketing are among the Ministry of Agriculture's programs. The ministry has a wide infrastructure in the provincial centers, with an agricultural branch in each province and an agricultural affairs department in each district. These agencies work to develop and modernize agricultural practices, increase crop yields, enhance gardening, educate farmers, gardeners, and livestock, and boost dairy products through artificial insemination.

B. Significance of the study

An online survey through Google form was used to perform the research, with the questionnaire being sent to a variety of employees of MAIL based in center and province level. The study concentrates generally on impact of training and development on performance of employees and organization. The importance of this research stemmed from the following goals: to find out whether T&D change the behaviour, skills and knowledge of employees and bring productivity to organization, to evaluate that T&D make the employees creative, to examine whether training help the employees to promote to higher positions, to analyze that whether T&D change the behavior and personality of the employees, to find out that does employees need assistance of supervisor after training, to assess that whether T&D avoid absenteeism in organization, to observe that whether employees feel of pride after training, to know that does T&D make the employees to be loyal and committed to the organization, to evaluate the satisfaction of employees after training, to evaluate that does training avoid turnover of employees in organization, to assess that whether training method and available materials were satisfactory, to evaluate that whether training was based on the needs of employees and objective of the organization, and know the behavior and method of trainers. Based on the researches which have been done related to this above topic prove that T&D change the skills and knowledge of employees and speed up performance of employees in organization.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A well-structured online questionnaire was prepared and distributed among central and provincial level employees of Ministry of agriculture, irrigation and livestock of Afghanistan. This chapter includes a review of the study, the nature and method of data collection, the sampling process, and the use of analytical or statistical instruments to analyze the data in order to meet the objective of the study.

- A. Description of the study area
- B. Nature and source of data
- C. Sampling procedure and data collection
- D. Analytical instruments adopted

A. Description of the study area

This study was done online at Ministry of agriculture, irrigation and livestock. MAIL is one of the key ministry of Afghanistan which operates in center as well as in province level. It has total employees of 7669 which 1968 of them are

based in central level and 5701 of them are based in provincial level. Till now no one has researched on impact of T&D on performance of employees and organization at MAIL, so this is really helpful for MAIL, especially for its human resource department to arrange all aspects related to T&D and based on this organize their capacity building programs effectively and efficiently.

B. Nature and source of data

Data was collected from primary as well as secondary sources. The study was focused on primary data. The primary data relevant to the socio-demographic status, and perception of the employees respect to the T&D was collected through Google form questionnaire. The target employees were those who were working in technical and administrative directorates of MAIL in center and province level only. The online questionnaires were shared with employees personally and received responses from 72 of employees of MAIL.

C. Sampling procedure and data collection

Sample: 72 respondents (employees of MAIL)

In the current analysis, a convenient sampling approach was used based on the existence and degree of data availability and time. The current study used an exploratory research model because it provides a more objective view of the employee's decision-making process by evaluating different factors such change in knowledge, change in skills, change in attitudes, and change in personality etc after training.

D. Analytical instruments adopted

For data analysis, data was collected through questionnaire and was generated in excel program and used for the following method of analysis.

- a) Frequency distribution
- b) Tabular analysis
- c) Factor analysis using PCA (Principle Component Analysis)

a) Frequency distribution:

A frequency distribution is a list, table, or pie chart that shows how many different outcomes occur in a sample. The frequency or count of occurrences of values within a particular category or interval is included in each table entry.

b) Tabular analysis:

Tabular analysis, in its broadest sense, refers to any analysis that employs tables, which involves almost any type of quantitative analysis. It only applies to the nominal and ordered variables in the analysis.

c) Factor analysis using PCA (Principle Component Analysis):

PCA is being used in analysis of exploratory data and predictive model creation. It's widely used for dimensionality reduction, where each data point is projected onto just the first few principal components to produce lower-dimensional data while maintaining as much variance as possible. The data was generated in excel program and upload in Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS)

to take out the result. The purpose of applying PCA was to understand the factors which influence performance,

knowledge, behavior, and satisfaction and of employees.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Regression Test to check the significance of the hypothesis

In order to check the impact of T&D on the performance of employees and organization Regression analysis will be used. The alternative hypothesis will be tested using regression analysis in SPSS. The following tables show the result for three hypotheses.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.583a	.340	.301	.635

Table 1: Regression: For Hypothesis 1.

a. Predictors: (Constant), Training and Development

Source: Own calculation of the author from primary data

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	13.936	4	3.484	8.629	.000 ^b
	Residual	27.051	67	.404		

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of Organization

b. Predictors (Constant): Training and Development

Table 2: ANOVA for Hypothesis 1

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.106	.962		1.150	.254
	T&D make employees creative in organization	.470	.132	.440	3.562	.001
	Training promote to higher positions	-.029	.105	-.036	-.277	.783
	T&D affect personality and attitude	.109	.309	.040	.352	.726
	Need to supervisor after training	.239	.152	.173	1.576	.120
	changes in performance after training	.227	.141	.177	1.610	.112

Table 3. Coefficient for Hypothesis 1

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of Organization

Source: Own calculation of the author from primary data

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.596 ^a	.355	.295	.638

Table 4: Regression: Hypothesis 2

a. Predictors: (Constant), Training and Development

Source: Own calculation of the author from primary data

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	14.538	6	2.423	5.955	.000 ^b
Residual	26.448	65	.407		
Total	40.986	71			

Table 5: Anova For Hypothesis 2

- a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Training and Development

Source: Own calculation of the author from primary data

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.382	.931		.411	.683
T&D avoid absenteeism of employees in organization	.091	.122	.094	.747	.458
feel sense of pride in job after training	.135	.307	.049	.440	.661
T&D make employees loyal and committed to Organization	.456	.127	.427	3.602	.001
T&D avoid turnover of employees in organization	.139	.119	.141	1.164	.249
Need more training in the future in the same platform	.068	.100	.075	.679	.500
Satisfaction of supervisor with your job performance after training	.120	.136	.096	.885	.380

Table 6: Coefficient for Hypothesis 2

- a. Dependent Variable: Training and Development

Source: Own calculation of the author from primary data

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.576 ^a	.332	.270	.553

Table 7. Regression: Hypothesis 3

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Design and delivery of training

Source: Own calculation of the author from primary data

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	9.871	6	1.645	5.372	.000 ^b
Residual	19.906	65	.306		
Total	29.778	71			

Table 8. Anova for Hypothesis 3

- a. Dependent Variable: Behavior and Knowledge of Employees
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Design and delivery of training

Source: Own calculation of the author from primary data

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.705	.682		1.034	.305
1 Training related materials available in class sufficiently	.177	.168	.129	1.055	.296
Clear direction by trainer during training to participants	.240	.116	.232	2.068	.043
Training prepared based on the needs of employees	.188	.128	.200	1.470	.146
Trainer's communication with all trainees	-.084	.119	-.091	-.706	.483
T&D was according to the objective of the Organization	.260	.106	.309	2.441	.017
Duration of training enough for trainees	.088	.148	.065	.600	.551

Table 9: Coefficient for Hypothesis 3

a. Dependent Variable: Behavior and Knowledge of Employees

B. Summary of Three Hypotheses

- **Hypothesis 1:** Regression result in this hypothesis specify that overall there is statistically positive relationship between performance of Organization (dependent variable) and T&D or independent variable (Sig = .000 which is less than 0.05) and R = .583 which is 58 %). R is correlation between dependent variable and independent variables in model summary of regression. Value of R is significant in the range of 0 to 1. Model summary and Anova tables look at regression analysis overall, however coefficient table look at regression analysis individually.
- **Hypothesis 2:** Regression result in this hypothesis specify that overall there is statistically positive relationship between satisfaction or dependent variable and T&D or independent variable (Sig = .000 which is less than 0.05) and (R = .596 which is 60%). R is correlation between dependent variable and independent variables in model summary of regression. Value of R is significant in the range of 0 to 1. Model summary and Anova tables look at regression analysis overall, however coefficient table look at regression analysis individually.
- **Hypothesis 3:** Regression result in this hypothesis specify that overall there is statistically positive relationship between Behavior and Knowledge of Employees or dependent variable and satisfaction or independent variable (Sig = .000 which is less than 0.05) and (R = .576 which is 58%). R is correlation between dependent variable and independent variables in model summary of regression. Value of R is significant in the range of 0 to 1. Model summary and Anova tables look at regression analysis overall, however coefficient table look at regression analysis individually.

IV. CONCLUSION

Any organization's sustainability depends on its ability to train its employees. It's also essential for employees' successful performance, their ability to adapt to an evolving and demanding business climate and technology for improved performance, and their knowledge to improve innovative and problem-solving skills. Organizational performance benefits from T&D. the purpose of this study is to evaluate the impact of T&D on performance of employees and organization at MAIL. This consist (1) finding out whether training and development affect performance of employees and organization, (2) to evaluate relationship between training and satisfaction of employees, (3) to identify that design and delivery of training method change the knowledge and behavior of the employees. Overall outcome for Hypothesis indicate that, **H₁**: proved that T&D has statistically significant impact on performance of employees and organization, **H₂**: proved that T&D has statistically significant impact on the satisfaction of the employees, **H₃**: proved that design and delivery of training has statistically significant impact on behavior and knowledge of employees. The results of this study indicated that T&D have an effect on employee job performance. This finding is in accordance with previous management research on T&D. Different questions are posed to the respondents and thus analyzed in order to obtain more detailed knowledge of T&D from the sample. These questions are participation of employees in training, demographic questions, location of the training, training frequency, types of training beneficial, impact of training on the creativity of the employees, impact of training on the performance of employees and organization, effect of T&D on the promotion, attitudes and personality of employees, need for the help of supervisor after training, impact of training on

the skills and knowledge of employees, effect of training in reduction of absenteeism and turnover in the organization, sense of pride in job after training, effect of T&D on the commitment and loyalty of the employees, satisfaction of employees to stay for long time with organization after T&D, need of more training for employees in the future, supervisors satisfaction from their subordinates after training, satisfaction of employees from method and availability of the training materials in class, communication and direction of trainers during the training, and whether training established based on the needs of the employees and objective of the organization. Employee participation in training suggest that MAIL has strong and perhaps consistent strategies about T&D, as the all of respondents confirmed that they have received training and that the majority of them were provided with opportunities to learn as part of the company's policy for all employees.

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